

1. Kết quả hồi quy SGMM 2 bước – robust

1.1. Mô hình M1

Dynamic panel-data estimation, two-step system GMM

Group variable: id	Number of obs	=	208
Time variable : year	Number of groups	=	26
Number of instruments = 24	Obs per group: min	=	8
Wald chi2(7) = 598.30	avg	=	8.00
Prob > chi2 = 0.000	max	=	8

car	Corrected		z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
	Coefficient	std. err.				
car						
L1.	.6134516	.1231342	4.98	0.000	.372113	.8547903
ow5	-.0309883	.011124	-2.79	0.005	-.052791	-.0091857
ow5_lev	.0024892	.0009239	2.69	0.007	.0006783	.0043001
size	-.0117359	.0042254	-2.78	0.005	-.0200176	-.0034542
roa	.6533573	.5387752	1.21	0.225	-.4026227	1.709337
lev	-.0020617	.0009763	-2.11	0.035	-.0039753	-.0001481
liq	-.0531571	.0462105	-1.15	0.250	-.143728	.0374137
_cons	.1324676	.0369436	3.59	0.000	.0600594	.2048758

Instruments for first differences equation

Standard

D.(L.ow5 L.ow5_lev L.size D.roa D2.lev)

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

L(1/2).(L.car L2.ow5 L2.ow5_lev L2.roa L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Instruments for levels equation

Standard

_cons

L.ow5 L.ow5_lev L.size D.roa D2.lev

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

D.(L.car L2.ow5 L2.ow5_lev L2.roa L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: z = -2.60 Pr > z = 0.009

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: z = -0.33 Pr > z = 0.742

Sargan test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 12.90 Prob > chi2 = 0.680

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments.)

Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 18.70 Prob > chi2 = 0.285

(Robust, but can be weakened by many instruments.)

Difference-in-Hansen tests of exogeneity of instrument subsets:

GMM instruments for levels

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 11.51 Prob > chi2 = 0.319

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(6) = 7.19 Prob > chi2 = 0.304

iv(L.ow5 L.ow5_lev L.size D.roa D2.lev)

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(11) = 9.72 Prob > chi2 = 0.555

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 8.97 Prob > chi2 = 0.110

1.2. Mô hình M2

Dynamic panel-data estimation, two-step system GMM

Group variable: id	Number of obs	=	208
Time variable : year	Number of groups	=	26
Number of instruments = 24	Obs per group: min	=	8
Wald chi2(7) = 1424.98	avg	=	8.00
Prob > chi2 = 0.000	max	=	8

car	Coefficient	Corrected std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
car						
L1.	.646388	.100061	6.46	0.000	.4502721	.8425039
ow5	-.0333282	.0071317	-4.67	0.000	-.0473062	-.0193503
ow5_lev	.0026245	.0006331	4.15	0.000	.0013836	.0038654
size	-.0122812	.0028865	-4.25	0.000	-.0179388	-.0066237
roe	.0869435	.0324485	2.68	0.007	.0233457	.1505413
lev	-.0023355	.0006928	-3.37	0.001	-.0036933	-.0009776
liq	-.0443435	.0223789	-1.98	0.048	-.0882053	-.0004818
_cons	.1300065	.0299914	4.33	0.000	.0712245	.1887886

Instruments for first differences equation

Standard

D.(L.ow5 L.ow5_lev L.size D.roe D2.lev)

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

L(1/2).(L.car L2.ow5 L2.ow5_lev L2.roe L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Instruments for levels equation

Standard

_cons

L.ow5 L.ow5_lev L.size D.roe D2.lev

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

D.(L.car L2.ow5 L2.ow5_lev L2.roe L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: z = -2.73 Pr > z = 0.006

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: z = -0.21 Pr > z = 0.837

Sargan test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 13.27 Prob > chi2 = 0.653

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments.)

Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 13.98 Prob > chi2 = 0.600

(Robust, but can be weakened by many instruments.)

Difference-in-Hansen tests of exogeneity of instrument subsets:

GMM instruments for levels

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 11.33 Prob > chi2 = 0.332

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(6) = 2.65 Prob > chi2 = 0.852

iv(L.ow5 L.ow5_lev L.size D.roe D2.lev)

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(11) = 10.80 Prob > chi2 = 0.460

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 3.18 Prob > chi2 = 0.673

1.3. Mô hình M3

Dynamic panel-data estimation, two-step system GMM

Group variable: id	Number of obs	=	208
Time variable : year	Number of groups	=	26
Number of instruments = 24	Obs per group: min	=	8
Wald chi2(7) = 383.73	avg	=	8.00
Prob > chi2 = 0.000	max	=	8

car	Corrected		z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
	Coefficient	std. err.				
car						
L1.	.4972576	.1219801	4.08	0.000	.2581809	.7363342
ow5	-.0320601	.0079281	-4.04	0.000	-.0475989	-.0165214
ow5_lev	.002318	.0006163	3.76	0.000	.00111	.003526
size	-.0135364	.003928	-3.45	0.001	-.0212352	-.0058377
cir	-.0301595	.0106372	-2.84	0.005	-.0510079	-.009311
lev	-.0023427	.0006405	-3.66	0.000	-.0035981	-.0010874
liq	-.0717581	.0212467	-3.38	0.001	-.1134008	-.0301153
_cons	.1846385	.0436005	4.23	0.000	.0991831	.270094

Instruments for first differences equation

Standard

D.(L.ow5 L.ow5_lev L.size D.cir D2.lev)

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

L(1/2).(L.car L2.ow5 L2.ow5_lev L2.cir L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Instruments for levels equation

Standard

_cons

L.ow5 L.ow5_lev L.size D.cir D2.lev

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

D.(L.car L2.ow5 L2.ow5_lev L2.cir L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: z = -2.41 Pr > z = 0.016

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: z = -0.70 Pr > z = 0.481

Sargan test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 21.61 Prob > chi2 = 0.156

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments.)

Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 11.35 Prob > chi2 = 0.788

(Robust, but can be weakened by many instruments.)

Difference-in-Hansen tests of exogeneity of instrument subsets:

GMM instruments for levels

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 9.32 Prob > chi2 = 0.502

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(6) = 2.03 Prob > chi2 = 0.917

iv(L.ow5 L.ow5_lev L.size D.cir D2.lev)

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(11) = 9.03 Prob > chi2 = 0.619

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 2.32 Prob > chi2 = 0.804

1.4. Mô hình M4

Dynamic panel-data estimation, two-step system GMM

Group variable: id	Number of obs	=	208
Time variable : year	Number of groups	=	26
Number of instruments = 24	Obs per group: min	=	8
Wald chi2(7) = 423.93	avg	=	8.00
Prob > chi2 = 0.000	max	=	8

car	Corrected		z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
	Coefficient	std. err.				
car						
L1.	.5991161	.1010814	5.93	0.000	.4010002	.797232
ow10	-.0285188	.0114489	-2.49	0.013	-.0509582	-.0060793
ow10_lev	.002366	.0008004	2.96	0.003	.0007973	.0039347
size	-.0102649	.0029442	-3.49	0.000	-.0160354	-.0044943
roa	.5905774	.4245398	1.39	0.164	-.2415053	1.42266
lev	-.0019766	.0009812	-2.01	0.044	-.0038997	-.0000534
liq	-.050605	.048817	-1.04	0.300	-.1462845	.0450744
_cons	.1249193	.0382941	3.26	0.001	.0498642	.1999743

Instruments for first differences equation

Standard

D.(L.ow10 L.ow10_lev L.size D.roa D2.lev)

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

L(1/2).(L2.car L2.ow10 L2.ow10_lev L2.roa L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Instruments for levels equation

Standard

_cons

L.ow10 L.ow10_lev L.size D.roa D2.lev

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

D.(L2.car L2.ow10 L2.ow10_lev L2.roa L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: z = -2.77 Pr > z = 0.006

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: z = -0.33 Pr > z = 0.741

Sargan test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 15.57 Prob > chi2 = 0.483

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments.)

Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 17.64 Prob > chi2 = 0.345

(Robust, but can be weakened by many instruments.)

Difference-in-Hansen tests of exogeneity of instrument subsets:

GMM instruments for levels

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 13.84 Prob > chi2 = 0.181

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(6) = 3.80 Prob > chi2 = 0.704

iv(L.ow10 L.ow10_lev L.size D.roa D2.lev)

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(11) = 13.19 Prob > chi2 = 0.281

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 4.45 Prob > chi2 = 0.487

1.5. Mô hình M5

Dynamic panel-data estimation, two-step system GMM

Group variable: id	Number of obs	=	208
Time variable : year	Number of groups	=	26
Number of instruments = 24	Obs per group: min	=	8
Wald chi2(7) = 774.79	avg	=	8.00
Prob > chi2 = 0.000	max	=	8

car	Corrected		z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
	Coefficient	std. err.				
car						
L1.	.6453998	.0850016	7.59	0.000	.4787997	.8119998
ow10	-.0304798	.0060502	-5.04	0.000	-.042338	-.0186216
ow10_lev	.0024702	.0005546	4.45	0.000	.0013832	.0035573
size	-.0117216	.0026786	-4.38	0.000	-.0169715	-.0064717
roe	.0881173	.0250714	3.51	0.000	.0389782	.1372565
lev	-.0021588	.0006909	-3.12	0.002	-.0035129	-.0008046
liq	-.0359688	.0201194	-1.79	0.074	-.0754021	.0034645
_cons	.1227993	.0277249	4.43	0.000	.0684596	.177139

Instruments for first differences equation

Standard

D.(L.ow10 L.ow10_lev L.size D.roe D2.lev)

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

L(1/2).(L2.car L2.ow10 L2.ow10_lev L2.roe L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Instruments for levels equation

Standard

_cons

L.ow10 L.ow10_lev L.size D.roe D2.lev

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

D.(L2.car L2.ow10 L2.ow10_lev L2.roe L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: z = -2.81 Pr > z = 0.005

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: z = -0.18 Pr > z = 0.858

Sargan test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 16.29 Prob > chi2 = 0.433

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments.)

Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 14.36 Prob > chi2 = 0.572

(Robust, but can be weakened by many instruments.)

Difference-in-Hansen tests of exogeneity of instrument subsets:

GMM instruments for levels

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 13.00 Prob > chi2 = 0.223

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(6) = 1.36 Prob > chi2 = 0.968

iv(L.ow10 L.ow10_lev L.size D.roe D2.lev)

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(11) = 11.23 Prob > chi2 = 0.425

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 3.14 Prob > chi2 = 0.679

1.6. Mô hình M6

Dynamic panel-data estimation, two-step system GMM

Group variable: id	Number of obs	=	208
Time variable : year	Number of groups	=	26
Number of instruments = 24	Obs per group: min	=	8
Wald chi2(7) = 213.66	avg	=	8.00
Prob > chi2 = 0.000	max	=	8

car	Corrected		z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
	Coefficient	std. err.				
car						
L1.	.5546528	.0771629	7.19	0.000	.4034163	.7058894
ow10	-.0268556	.007999	-3.36	0.001	-.0425334	-.0111778
ow10_lev	.0019856	.0006375	3.11	0.002	.0007361	.0032352
size	-.0130889	.0034876	-3.75	0.000	-.0199246	-.0062533
cir	-.0292877	.0118983	-2.46	0.014	-.052608	-.0059674
lev	-.0019064	.0006191	-3.08	0.002	-.0031199	-.000693
liq	-.0887717	.0302591	-2.93	0.003	-.1480785	-.029465
_cons	.1714536	.0358704	4.78	0.000	.1011489	.2417583

Instruments for first differences equation

Standard

D.(L.ow10 L.ow10_lev L.size D.cir D2.lev)

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

L(1/2).(L2.car L2.ow10 L2.ow10_lev L2.cir L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Instruments for levels equation

Standard

_cons

L.ow10 L.ow10_lev L.size D.cir D2.lev

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

D.(L2.car L2.ow10 L2.ow10_lev L2.cir L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: z = -2.77 Pr > z = 0.006

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: z = -0.64 Pr > z = 0.520

Sargan test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 22.80 Prob > chi2 = 0.119

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments.)

Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(16) = 16.94 Prob > chi2 = 0.390

(Robust, but can be weakened by many instruments.)

Difference-in-Hansen tests of exogeneity of instrument subsets:

GMM instruments for levels

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 11.10 Prob > chi2 = 0.350

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(6) = 5.84 Prob > chi2 = 0.441

iv(L.ow10 L.ow10_lev L.size D.cir D2.lev)

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(11) = 9.32 Prob > chi2 = 0.593

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 7.62 Prob > chi2 = 0.179

1.7. Mô hình M7

Dynamic panel-data estimation, two-step system GMM

Group variable: id	Number of obs	=	208
Time variable : year	Number of groups	=	26
Number of instruments = 23	Obs per group: min	=	8
Wald chi2(7) = 350.70	avg	=	8.00
Prob > chi2 = 0.000	max	=	8

car	Corrected		z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
	Coefficient	std. err.				
car						
L1.	.5727646	.1153491	4.97	0.000	.3466845	.7988447
ow65	-.0140998	.0226054	-0.62	0.533	-.0584055	.030206
ow65_lev	.0019387	.0012784	1.52	0.129	-.0005668	.0044443
size	-.0165769	.0080079	-2.07	0.038	-.0322722	-.0008817
roa	.9094633	.5213647	1.74	0.081	-.1123928	1.931319
lev	-.0018348	.0009402	-1.95	0.051	-.0036776	8.02e-06
liq	-.0561425	.0459551	-1.22	0.222	-.1462129	.0339278
_cons	.1558076	.0521301	2.99	0.003	.0536345	.2579808

Instruments for first differences equation

Standard

D.(L.ow65 L.ow65_lev L.size D.roa D2.lev)

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

L(1/2).(L2.car L2.ow65 L2.ow65_lev L2.roa L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Instruments for levels equation

Standard

_cons

L.ow65 L.ow65_lev L.size D.roa D2.lev

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

D.(L2.car L2.ow65 L2.ow65_lev L2.roa L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: z = -2.70 Pr > z = 0.007

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: z = -0.35 Pr > z = 0.726

Sargan test of overid. restrictions: chi2(15) = 14.81 Prob > chi2 = 0.465

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments.)

Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(15) = 14.11 Prob > chi2 = 0.517

(Robust, but can be weakened by many instruments.)

Difference-in-Hansen tests of exogeneity of instrument subsets:

GMM instruments for levels

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 10.59 Prob > chi2 = 0.391

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 3.52 Prob > chi2 = 0.620

iv(L.ow65 L.ow65_lev L.size D.roa D2.lev)

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 11.57 Prob > chi2 = 0.315

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 2.54 Prob > chi2 = 0.770

1.8. Mô hình M8

Dynamic panel-data estimation, two-step system GMM

Group variable: id	Number of obs	=	208
Time variable : year	Number of groups	=	26
Number of instruments = 23	Obs per group: min	=	8
Wald chi2(7) = 219.60	avg	=	8.00
Prob > chi2 = 0.000	max	=	8

car	Corrected					
	Coefficient	std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
car						
L1.	.6445624	.1034531	6.23	0.000	.441798	.8473267
ow65	-.0253184	.0230277	-1.10	0.272	-.0704518	.019815
ow65_lev	.0023945	.001621	1.48	0.140	-.0007827	.0055716
size	-.0127796	.0089136	-1.43	0.152	-.0302499	.0046908
roe	.0997412	.042876	2.33	0.020	.0157057	.1837767
lev	-.0021413	.0009316	-2.30	0.022	-.0039671	-.0003154
liq	-.0174927	.0412484	-0.42	0.672	-.098338	.0633527
_cons	.1230834	.0567715	2.17	0.030	.0118133	.2343536

Instruments for first differences equation

Standard

D.(L.ow65 L.ow65_lev L.size D.roe D2.lev)

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

L(1/2).(L2.car L2.ow65 L2.ow65_lev L2.roe L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Instruments for levels equation

Standard

_cons

L.ow65 L.ow65_lev L.size D.roe D2.lev

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

D.(L2.car L2.ow65 L2.ow65_lev L2.roe L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: z = -2.68 Pr > z = 0.007

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: z = -0.17 Pr > z = 0.865

Sargan test of overid. restrictions: chi2(15) = 14.36 Prob > chi2 = 0.498

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments.)

Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(15) = 13.76 Prob > chi2 = 0.544

(Robust, but can be weakened by many instruments.)

Difference-in-Hansen tests of exogeneity of instrument subsets:

GMM instruments for levels

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 12.16 Prob > chi2 = 0.275

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 1.60 Prob > chi2 = 0.901

iv(L.ow65 L.ow65_lev L.size D.roe D2.lev)

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 12.08 Prob > chi2 = 0.280

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 1.67 Prob > chi2 = 0.892

1.9. Mô hình M9

Dynamic panel-data estimation, two-step system GMM

Group variable: id	Number of obs	=	208
Time variable : year	Number of groups	=	26
Number of instruments = 23	Obs per group: min	=	8
Wald chi2(7) = 230.50	avg	=	8.00
Prob > chi2 = 0.000	max	=	8

car	Corrected		z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
	Coefficient	std. err.				
car						
L1.	.5445035	.1536588	3.54	0.000	.2433378	.8456693
ow65	-.0253158	.0271619	-0.93	0.351	-.0785521	.0279206
ow65_lev	.0019453	.0014024	1.39	0.165	-.0008035	.004694
size	-.0111636	.0062689	-1.78	0.075	-.0234505	.0011233
cir	-.0214549	.0124517	-1.72	0.085	-.0458597	.0029499
lev	-.0020656	.0008407	-2.46	0.014	-.0037134	-.0004179
liq	-.0644766	.044594	-1.45	0.148	-.1518793	.0229261
_cons	.1565843	.058984	2.65	0.008	.0409779	.2721908

Instruments for first differences equation

Standard

D.(L.ow65 L.ow65_lev L.size D.cir D2.lev)

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

L(1/2).(L2.car L2.ow65 L2.ow65_lev L2.cir L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Instruments for levels equation

Standard

_cons

L.ow65 L.ow65_lev L.size D.cir D2.lev

GMM-type (missing=0, separate instruments for each period unless collapsed)

D.(L2.car L2.ow65 L2.ow65_lev L2.cir L2.lev L2.liq) collapsed

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: z = -2.41 Pr > z = 0.016

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: z = -0.62 Pr > z = 0.533

Sargan test of overid. restrictions: chi2(15) = 21.10 Prob > chi2 = 0.134

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments.)

Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(15) = 11.81 Prob > chi2 = 0.693

(Robust, but can be weakened by many instruments.)

Difference-in-Hansen tests of exogeneity of instrument subsets:

GMM instruments for levels

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 10.54 Prob > chi2 = 0.394

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 1.27 Prob > chi2 = 0.938

iv(L.ow65 L.ow65_lev L.size D.cir D2.lev)

Hansen test excluding group: chi2(10) = 8.51 Prob > chi2 = 0.579

Difference (null H = exogenous): chi2(5) = 3.31 Prob > chi2 = 0.653

4. Kết quả mô hình kiểm tra tính vững thông qua hồi quy Bayes đối với M2, M3, M5, M6

1.1. Kết quả hồi quy Bayes đối với M2

Model summary

Likelihood:

`car ~ normal(xb_car, {e.car:sigma2})`

Priors:

```
{car:lagcar} ~ normal(.6393423, 0.000001) (1)
{car:ow5} ~ normal(-.0342626, 0.000001) (1)
{car:ow5_lev} ~ normal(.0027007, 0.000001) (1)
{car:size} ~ normal(-.0120624, 0.000001) (1)
{car:roe} ~ normal(.0823114, 0.000001) (1)
{car:liq} ~ normal(-.0461948, 0.000001) (1)
{car:lev} ~ normal(-.0024421, 0.000001) (1)
{car:_cons} ~ normal(.1317654, 0.000001) (1)
{U0} ~ normal(0, {U0:sigma2}) (1)
{e.car:sigma2} ~ igamma(.01, .01)
```

Hyperprior:

`{U0:sigma2} ~ igamma(.01, .01)`

(1) Parameters are elements of the linear form `xb_car`.

Bayesian multilevel regression	Number of chains	=	2
Metropolis-Hastings and Gibbs sampling	Per MCMC chain:		
	Iterations	=	204,991
	Burn-in	=	5,000
	Sample size	=	20,000
Group variable: id	Number of groups	=	26
	Obs per group:		
	min	=	9
	avg	=	9.0
	max	=	9
	Number of obs	=	234
	<u>Avg</u> acceptance rate	=	.9336
	<u>Avg</u> efficiency: min	=	.0951
	avg	=	.731
	max	=	1
<u>Log marginal-likelihood</u>	<u>Max Gelman-Rubin R_c</u>	=	1.002

mean : {car:ow5} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow5} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow5_lev} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow5_lev} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:size} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:size} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:roe} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:roe} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:liq} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:liq} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:lev} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:lev} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:_cons} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:_cons} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

car	_cons	1.000017
e.car	sigma2	.9999771
car	roe	.9999759

Convergence rule: $R_c < 1.1$

1.2. Kết quả hồi quy Bayes đối với M3

Multilevel structure

id
{U0}: random intercepts

Model summary

Likelihood:
car ~ normal(xb_car,{e.car:sigma2})

Priors:

```

{car:lagcar} ~ normal(.4972576,0.000001)      (1)
  {car:ow5} ~ normal(-.0320601,0.000001)      (1)
{car:ow5_lev} ~ normal(.002318,0.000001)      (1)
  {car:size} ~ normal(-.0135364,0.000001)     (1)
  {car:cir} ~ normal(-.0301595,0.000001)     (1)
  {car:liq} ~ normal(-.0717581,0.000001)     (1)
  {car:lev} ~ normal(-.0023427,0.000001)     (1)
{car:_cons} ~ normal(.1846385,0.000001)      (1)
  {U0} ~ normal(0,{U0:sigma2})                (1)
{e.car:sigma2} ~ igamma(.01,.01)

```

Hyperprior:

```
{U0:sigma2} ~ igamma(.01,.01)
```

(1) Parameters are elements of the linear form `xb_car`.

Bayesian multilevel regression	Number of chains	=	2
Metropolis-Hastings and Gibbs sampling	Per MCMC chain:		
	Iterations	=	204,991
	Burn-in	=	5,000
	Sample size	=	20,000
Group variable: <code>id</code>	Number of groups	=	26
	Obs per group:		
	min	=	9
	avg	=	9.0
	max	=	9
	Number of obs	=	234
	<u>Avg</u> acceptance rate	=	.9335
	<u>Avg</u> efficiency: min	=	.08933
	avg	=	.7319
	max	=	1
<u>Log marginal-likelihood</u>	<u>Max Gelman-Rubin R_c</u>	=	1

mean : {car:ow5} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow5} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow5_lev} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	.999975	0.00500	.000025

mean : {car:ow5_lev} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	.000025	0.00500	.000025

mean : {car:size} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:size} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:cir} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:cir} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:liq} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:liq} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:lev} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:lev} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:_cons} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:_cons} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

Gelman-Rubin convergence diagnostic

Number of chains = 2
 MCMC size, per chain = 20,000
 Max Gelman-Rubin Rc = 1.000342

	Rc
car	
size	1.000342
ow5_lev	1.000211
ow5	1.00007
lagcar	1.000041
liq	1.000038
_cons	1.000035
id	
U0:sigma2	1.000025
car	
lev	.9999975
e.car	
sigma2	.9999912
car	
cir	.9999759

Convergence rule: Rc < 1.1

1.3. Kết quả hồi quy Bayes đối với M5

Multilevel structure

id
 {U0}: random intercepts

Model summary

Likelihood:

car ~ normal(xb_car, {e.car:sigma2})

Priors:

{car:lagcar} ~ normal(.6426021, 0.000001)	(1)
{car:ow10} ~ normal(-.0307103, 0.000001)	(1)
{car:ow10_lev} ~ normal(.0024968, 0.000001)	(1)
{car:size} ~ normal(-.0115243, 0.000001)	(1)
{car:roe} ~ normal(.0857126, 0.000001)	(1)
{car:liq} ~ normal(-.0369421, 0.000001)	(1)
{car:lev} ~ normal(-.0022148, 0.000001)	(1)
{car:_cons} ~ normal(.1231321, 0.000001)	(1)
{U0} ~ normal(0, {U0:sigma2})	(1)
{e.car:sigma2} ~ igamma(.01, .01)	

Hyperprior:

{U0:sigma2} ~ igamma(.01, .01)

(1) Parameters are elements of the linear form xb_car.

Bayesian multilevel regression	Number of chains	=	2
Metropolis-Hastings and Gibbs sampling	Per MCMC chain:		
	Iterations	=	304,991
	Burn-in	=	5,000
	Sample size	=	30,000
Group variable: id	Number of groups	=	26
	Obs per group:		
	min	=	9
	avg	=	9.0
	max	=	9
	Number of obs	=	234
	<u>Avg</u> acceptance rate	=	.9337
	<u>Avg</u> efficiency: min	=	.09226
	avg	=	.7335
	max	=	1
<u>Log marginal-likelihood</u>	<u>Max Gelman-Rubin Rc</u>	=	1.001

mean : {car:ow10} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow10} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow10_lev} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow10_lev} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:size} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:size} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:roe} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:roe} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:liq} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:liq} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:lev} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:lev} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:_cons} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:_cons} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

Gelman-Rubin convergence diagnostic

Number of chains = 2
MCMC size, per chain = 30,000
Max Gelman-Rubin Rc = 1.000505

	Rc
car	
size	1.000505
ow10_lev	1.000328
ow10	1.000096
id	
U0:sigma2	1.000059
car	
lagcar	1.000039
lev	1.000026
_cons	1.000023
liq	1.000015
roe	.9999953
e.car	
sigma2	.9999869

Convergence rule: Rc < 1.1

1.4. Kết quả hồi quy Bayes đối với M6

Model summary

Likelihood:

```
car ~ normal(xb_car, {e.car:sigma2})
```

Priors:

```
{car:lagcar} ~ normal(.581372,0.000001) (1)
{car:ow10} ~ normal(-.026337,0.000001) (1)
{car:ow10_lev} ~ normal(.001929,0.000001) (1)
{car:size} ~ normal(-.0151953,0.000001) (1)
{car:cir} ~ normal(-.0424231,0.000001) (1)
{car:liq} ~ normal(-.0788171,0.000001) (1)
{car:lev} ~ normal(-.0016085,0.000001) (1)
{car:_cons} ~ normal(.1805495,0.000001) (1)
{U0} ~ normal(0, {U0:sigma2}) (1)
{e.car:sigma2} ~ igamma(.01, .01)
```

Hyperprior:

```
{U0:sigma2} ~ igamma(.01, .01)
```

(1) Parameters are elements of the linear form `xb_car`.

Bayesian multilevel regression	Number of chains	=	2
Metropolis-Hastings and Gibbs sampling	Per MCMC chain:		
	Iterations	=	304,991
	Burn-in	=	5,000
	Sample size	=	30,000
Group variable: <code>id</code>	Number of groups	=	26
	Obs per group:		
	min	=	9
	avg	=	9.0
	max	=	9
	Number of obs	=	234
	<u>Avg</u> acceptance rate	=	.9335
	<u>Avg</u> efficiency: min	=	.09088
	avg	=	.7367
	max	=	1
<u>Log marginal-likelihood</u>	<u>Max Gelman-Rubin R_c</u>	=	1

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE	Median	Equal-tailed [95% cred. interval]	
car						
lagcar	.5813723	.0009975	4.1e-06	.5813716	.5794283	.5833268
ow10	-.0263607	.001	4.1e-06	-.0263643	-.0283269	-.0243963
ow10_lev	.0017991	.0004935	4.0e-06	.0017996	.0008254	.0027628
size	-.0147497	.001372	.000019	-.0147521	-.0174394	-.0120646
cir	-.0421499	.0010004	4.1e-06	-.0421523	-.0441101	-.0401813
liq	-.0788448	.000998	4.1e-06	-.0788503	-.0807965	-.0768963
lev	-.0017696	.0004504	4.0e-06	-.0017683	-.0026513	-.0008875
_cons	.1805822	.0009963	4.1e-06	.1805797	.1786352	.1825426
id						
U0:sigma2	.0009617	.0002974	1.3e-06	.0009084	.0005435	.0016869
e.car						
sigma2	.0003397	.0000336	1.4e-07	.0003375	.0002804	.0004115

Note: Default priors are used for some model parameters.

Note: Default initial values are used for multiple chains.

mean : {car:lagcar} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:lagcar} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow10} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow10} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:ow10_lev} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	.9998333	0.01291	.0000527

mean : {car:ow10_lev} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	.0001667	0.01291	.0000527

mean : {car:size} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:size} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:cir} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:cir} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:liq} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

mean : {car:liq} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:lev} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	.0000667	0.00816	.0000333

mean : {car:lev} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	.9999333	0.00816	.0000333

mean : {car:_cons} > 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	1	0.00000	0

mean : {car:_cons} < 0

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE
mean	0	0.00000	0

Gelman–Rubin convergence diagnostic

Number of chains = 2
MCMC size, per chain = 30,000
Max Gelman–Rubin Rc = 1.000162

	Rc
car	
size	1.000162
ow10_lev	1.000134
ow10	1.000076
id	
U0:sigma2	1.000066
car	
lagcar	1.000042
_cons	1.000036
liq	1.000013
cir	1.000005
lev	1.000001
e.car	
sigma2	.9999992

Convergence rule: $Rc < 1.1$

2. Kết quả Mô hình DID và PSM

2.1. Mô hình DID

Treatment and time information

Time variable: **time1**Control: **bas = 0**Treatment: **bas = 1**

		Control	Treatment
Group			
	name1	12	11
Time			
	Minimum	122	125
	Maximum	122	125

Difference-in-differences regression
Data type: Longitudinal

Number of obs = **184**(Std. err. adjusted for **23** clusters in **name1**)

car		Coefficient	Robust std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]	
ATET							
	bas (1 vs 0)	.0016053	.0031825	0.50	0.619	-.0049948	.0082055

Note: ATET estimate adjusted for covariates, panel effects, and time effects.

Parallel-trends test (pretreatment time period)

H0: Linear trends are parallel

F(1, 22) = **0.48**Prob > F = **0.4964**

Granger causality test

H0: No effect in anticipation of treatment

F(2, 22) = 0.76

Prob > F = 0.4802

Fixed-effects (within) regression

Group variable: name1

Number of obs = 184

Number of groups = 23

R-squared:

Within = 0.2883

Between = 0.7143

Overall = 0.6223

Obs per group:

min = 8

avg = 8.0

max = 8

corr(u_i, Xb) = 0.3112

F(19, 22) = 105.48

Prob > F = 0.0000

(Std. err. adjusted for 23 clusters in name1)

car	Coefficient	Robust std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]	
lagcar	.1374132	.0886562	1.55	0.135	-.0464486	.321275
size	.001081	.0315824	0.03	0.973	-.0644168	.0665788
roa	.0823482	.7707572	0.11	0.916	-1.516104	1.680801
liq	.0778562	.029473	2.64	0.015	.016733	.1389793
lev	-.0027074	.0008978	-3.02	0.006	-.0045694	-.0008454
time1						
123	-.0027676	.003794	-0.73	0.473	-.0106357	.0051006
124	.0081503	.0079153	1.03	0.314	-.008265	.0245655
125	.0001462	.0047198	0.03	0.976	-.0096422	.0099345
126	.0050037	.0048922	1.02	0.318	-.0051421	.0151495
127	.000716	.0043995	0.16	0.872	-.0084079	.00984
128	.0020965	.0051388	0.41	0.687	-.0085608	.0127538
129	.0002037	.0060219	0.03	0.973	-.0122849	.0126923
_lead3	.0069128	.0099545	0.69	0.495	-.0137316	.0275572
_lead2	.0089319	.0081836	1.09	0.287	-.0080399	.0259037
_lag0	.0097207	.0068121	1.43	0.168	-.0044067	.023848
_lag1	.0022001	.0059679	0.37	0.716	-.0101766	.0145767
_lag2	.0049793	.0073788	0.67	0.507	-.0103233	.020282
_lag3	.0065002	.0070355	0.92	0.366	-.0080905	.0210909
_lag4	.0062113	.0075117	0.83	0.417	-.0093672	.0217897

_cons	.1090654	.1669683	0.65	0.520	-.2372057	.4553366
sigma_u	.011552					
sigma_e	.00972406					
rho	.58528571	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

Treatment and time information

Time variable: **time1**

Control: **bas = 0**

Treatment: **bas = 1**

	Control	Treatment
Group		
name1	12	11
Time		
Minimum	122	125
Maximum	122	125

Difference-in-differences regression

Number of obs = 184

Data type: Longitudinal

(Std. err. adjusted for 23 clusters in name1)

car	Coefficient	Robust std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]	
ATET						
bas						
(1 vs 0)	.0006527	.0031781	0.21	0.839	-.0059383	.0072436

Note: ATET estimate adjusted for covariates, panel effects, and time effects.

Parallel-trends test (pretreatment time period)

H0: Linear trends are parallel

F(1, 22) = 0.53

Prob > F = 0.4757

Granger causality test

H0: No effect in anticipation of treatment

F(2, 22) = 0.79

Prob > F = 0.4678

APPENDIX PHD THESIS _ LE HUU NGHIA

Fixed-effects (within) regression
Group variable: name1

Number of obs = 184
Number of groups = 23

R-squared:

Within = 0.2909
Between = 0.7120
Overall = 0.6205

Obs per group:

min = 8
avg = 8.0
max = 8

corr(u_i, Xb) = 0.3205

F(19, 22) = 35.48
Prob > F = 0.0000

(Std. err. adjusted for 23 clusters in name1)

car	Coefficient	Robust std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]	
lagcar	.1354981	.0902016	1.50	0.147	-.0515687	.3225648
size	.0041767	.0346073	0.12	0.905	-.0675945	.0759479
roe	-.0468025	.1035644	-0.45	0.656	-.2615819	.167977
liq	.0780636	.0296967	2.63	0.015	.0164764	.1396507
lev	-.0028314	.0008836	-3.20	0.004	-.0046638	-.000999
time1						
123	-.0025324	.0039518	-0.64	0.528	-.0107278	.0056631
124	.0079192	.0074511	1.06	0.299	-.0075334	.0233717
125	.0007219	.0048528	0.15	0.883	-.0093421	.0107859
126	.0047342	.0047657	0.99	0.331	-.0051493	.0146177
127	.0005822	.0044121	0.13	0.896	-.008568	.0097324
128	.0017603	.0053922	0.33	0.747	-.0094225	.0129432
129	.0000412	.0063306	0.01	0.995	-.0130877	.0131701
_lead3	.0077694	.0105278	0.74	0.468	-.014064	.0296028
_lead2	.009438	.0083992	1.12	0.273	-.0079809	.026857
_lag0	.0092386	.006278	1.47	0.155	-.0037812	.0222584
_lag1	.0013541	.0053467	0.25	0.802	-.0097342	.0124425
_lag2	.0041082	.0068939	0.60	0.557	-.0101889	.0184052
_lag3	.0057078	.0067043	0.85	0.404	-.008196	.0196117
_lag4	.0054097	.0069488	0.78	0.445	-.0090012	.0198206
_cons	.0959351	.1813	0.53	0.602	-.2800581	.4719283
sigma_u	.01164861					
sigma_e	.00970654					
rho	.59019543	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

Treatment and time information

Time variable: **time1**
 Control: **bas = 0**
 Treatment: **bas = 1**

	Control	Treatment
Group		
name1	12	11
Time		
Minimum	122	125
Maximum	122	125

Difference-in-differences regression
 Data type: Longitudinal

Number of obs = **184**

(Std. err. adjusted for **23** clusters in **name1**)

car	Coefficient	Robust std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]	
ATET						
bas						
(1 vs 0)	-.0005905	.0031461	-0.19	0.853	-.0071152	.0059343

Note: ATET estimate adjusted for covariates, panel effects, and time effects.

Parallel-trends test (pretreatment time period)

H0: Linear trends are parallel

F(1, 22) = 0.87

Prob > F = 0.3600

Granger causality test

H0: No effect in anticipation of treatment

F(2, 22) = 0.98

Prob > F = 0.3907

Fixed-effects (within) regression
 Group variable: name1

Number of obs = 184
 Number of groups = 23

R-squared:
 Within = 0.3291
 Between = 0.5860
 Overall = 0.5275

Obs per group:
 min = 8
 avg = 8.0
 max = 8

corr(u_i, Xb) = 0.2495

F(19, 22) = 146.38
 Prob > F = 0.0000

(Std. err. adjusted for 23 clusters in name1)

car	Coefficient	Robust std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]	
lagcar	.1302007	.0907299	1.44	0.165	-.0579615	.3183629
size	.0144613	.0338733	0.43	0.674	-.0557876	.0847103
cir	.0244457	.0160002	1.53	0.141	-.0087366	.057628
liq	.0782088	.0331585	2.36	0.028	.0094423	.1469752
lev	-.0029462	.0008668	-3.40	0.003	-.0047439	-.0011484
time1						
123	-.0008222	.0036483	-0.23	0.824	-.0083883	.0067439
124	.0085863	.0073954	1.16	0.258	-.0067509	.0239235
125	.0027308	.0046666	0.59	0.564	-.0069472	.0124088
126	.0041765	.0044026	0.95	0.353	-.0049539	.0133069
127	.0004551	.0042066	0.11	0.915	-.0082688	.0091791
128	.0016473	.0053278	0.31	0.760	-.0094019	.0126965
129	.0007647	.0059646	0.13	0.899	-.0116052	.0131345
_lead3	.0089635	.0096691	0.93	0.364	-.0110891	.029016
_lead2	.0098329	.0075583	1.30	0.207	-.0058421	.0255079
_lag0	.0077816	.0055713	1.40	0.176	-.0037726	.0193359
_lag1	.0007629	.005485	0.14	0.891	-.0106122	.0121381
_lag2	.0042093	.007276	0.58	0.569	-.0108802	.0192987
_lag3	.0057892	.0071244	0.81	0.425	-.008986	.0205644
_lag4	.0052809	.0068293	0.77	0.448	-.0088822	.019444
_cons	.0291801	.1842727	0.16	0.876	-.3529781	.4113384
sigma_u	.01363451					
sigma_e	.00944103					
rho	.67591876	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

2.2. Mô hình kiểm tra tính vững DID bằng PSM

Iteration 0: Log likelihood = -112.22905
 Iteration 1: Log likelihood = -96.053578
 Iteration 2: Log likelihood = -94.997931
 Iteration 3: Log likelihood = -94.990074
 Iteration 4: Log likelihood = -94.990072

Logistic regression

Number of obs = 184
 LR chi2(6) = 34.48
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
 Pseudo R2 = 0.1536

Log likelihood = -94.990072

bas	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
car	.9718154	19.89703	0.05	0.961	-38.02565	39.96928
lagcar	-7.79245	18.83556	-0.41	0.679	-44.70948	29.12458
size	1.133647	.5080255	2.23	0.026	.1379352	2.129359
roe	7.205826	9.853241	0.73	0.465	-12.10617	26.51782
liq	7.487543	3.986161	1.88	0.060	-.3251886	15.30027
lev	-.3556404	.1033399	-3.44	0.001	-.5581829	-.1530978
_cons	-4.148715	4.059053	-1.02	0.307	-12.10431	3.806883

29 . logit bas car lagcar size roa liq lev

Iteration 0: Log likelihood = -112.22905
 Iteration 1: Log likelihood = -95.907149
 Iteration 2: Log likelihood = -94.871312
 Iteration 3: Log likelihood = -94.864823
 Iteration 4: Log likelihood = -94.864822

Logistic regression

Number of obs = 184
 LR chi2(6) = 34.73
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
 Pseudo R2 = 0.1547

Log likelihood = -94.864822

bas	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
car	1.244417	19.64392	0.06	0.949	-37.25695	39.74579
lagcar	-7.911885	18.70378	-0.42	0.672	-44.57061	28.74685
size	1.110274	.5067557	2.19	0.028	.1170508	2.103497
roa	86.26585	97.39952	0.89	0.376	-104.6337	277.1654
liq	7.785533	4.015501	1.94	0.053	-.0847049	15.65577
lev	-.3286001	.1059189	-3.10	0.002	-.5361974	-.1210029
_cons	-4.402209	4.043528	-1.09	0.276	-12.32738	3.52296

Variable	Sample	Treated	Controls	Difference	S.E.	T-stat
car	Unmatched	.127107272	.115844961	.011262311	.003517442	3.20
	ATT	.126529629	.122371491	.004158138	.00379039	1.10

Note: S.E. does not take into account that the propensity score is estimated.

psmatch2: Treatment assignment	psmatch2: Common support		Total
	Off suppo	On suppor	
Untreated	0	129	129
Treated	1	54	55
Total	1	183	184

Iteration 0: Log likelihood = -112.22905
 Iteration 1: Log likelihood = -96.053578
 Iteration 2: Log likelihood = -94.997931
 Iteration 3: Log likelihood = -94.990074
 Iteration 4: Log likelihood = -94.990072

Logistic regression

Number of obs = 184
 LR chi2(6) = 34.48
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
 Pseudo R2 = 0.1536

Log likelihood = -94.990072

bas	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
car	.9718154	19.89703	0.05	0.961	-38.02565	39.96928
lagcar	-7.79245	18.83556	-0.41	0.679	-44.70948	29.12458
size	1.133647	.5080255	2.23	0.026	.1379352	2.129359
roe	7.205826	9.853241	0.73	0.465	-12.10617	26.51782
liq	7.487543	3.986161	1.88	0.060	-.3251886	15.30027
lev	-.3556404	.1033399	-3.44	0.001	-.5581829	-.1530978
_cons	-4.148715	4.059053	-1.02	0.307	-12.10431	3.806883

Variable	Sample	Treated	Controls	Difference	S.E.	T-stat
car	Unmatched	.127107272	.115844961	.011262311	.003517442	3.20
	ATT	.127107272	.122184561	.004922711	.004096739	1.20

Note: S.E. does not take into account that the propensity score is estimated.

psmatch2: Treatment assignment	psmatch2: Common support		Total
	On suppor		
Untreated	129		129
Treated	55		55
Total	184		184

Iteration 0: Log likelihood = -112.22905
 Iteration 1: Log likelihood = -96.063776
 Iteration 2: Log likelihood = -95.038629
 Iteration 3: Log likelihood = -95.032464
 Iteration 4: Log likelihood = -95.032463

Logistic regression

Number of obs = 184
 LR chi2(6) = 34.39
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
 Pseudo R2 = 0.1532

Log likelihood = -95.032463

bas	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
car	.9237254	20.11818	0.05	0.963	-38.50718	40.35463
lagcar	-8.78187	18.93369	-0.46	0.643	-45.89123	28.32749
size	1.049367	.5722601	1.83	0.067	-.0722425	2.170976
cir	-1.199867	1.817724	-0.66	0.509	-4.76254	2.362806
liq	7.379425	3.95861	1.86	0.062	-.3793074	15.13816
lev	-.3444527	.1028348	-3.35	0.001	-.5460051	-.1429002
_cons	-2.891552	4.666032	-0.62	0.535	-12.03681	6.253704

Variable	Sample	Treated	Controls	Difference	S.E.	T-stat
car	Unmatched	.127107272	.115844961	.011262311	.003517442	3.20
	ATT	.1263	.124081367	.002218633	.004112623	0.54

Note: S.E. does not take into account that the propensity score is estimated.

psmatch2: Treatment assignment	psmatch2: Common support		Total
	Off suppo	On suppor	
Untreated	0	129	129
Treated	1	54	55
Total	1	183	184

3. Thống kê cơ bản giá trị biến mô hình DID

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
car	207	.1182353	.0228606	.0839	.1932
lagcar	184	.1178435	.0232192	.0839	.1932
size	207	5.431901	.4832157	4.31322	6.40159
roa	207	.0034013	.0022591	-.00202	.01
roe	207	.0366099	.0220169	-.01338	.088
cir	207	.4248482	.1556242	.20312	1.28581
liq	207	.1559278	.05684	.05418	.41621
lev	207	10.77272	3.599216	4.61515	20.07479

4. Ma trận tự tương quan các biến trong mô hình DID

	car	lagcar	size	roa	roe	cir	liq
car	1.0000						
lagcar	0.8454 0.0000	1.0000					
size	-0.2957 0.0000	-0.3084 0.0000	1.0000				
roa	0.1789 0.0099	0.1441 0.0510	0.4004 0.0000	1.0000			
roe	-0.1436 0.0390	-0.1735 0.0185	0.5116 0.0000	0.8339 0.0000	1.0000		
cir	-0.0102 0.8839	-0.0304 0.6824	-0.6289 0.0000	-0.6327 0.0000	-0.6696 0.0000	1.0000	
liq	0.1982 0.0042	0.1925 0.0088	-0.4328 0.0000	-0.3198 0.0000	-0.2966 0.0000	0.3737 0.0000	1.0000
lev	-0.7221 0.0000	-0.7144 0.0000	0.2048 0.0031	-0.3785 0.0000	0.0484 0.4883	0.1409 0.0429	-0.0115 0.8691
lev							1.0000

